

A Clinical Study of Islanders to Determine Adverse Effects of Benzodiazepines and Mood-Related Memories on Memory Recall Performance

by: Steve Ahn

Order of Operations:

1. Introductory & Background Information
2. Data Exploration & Design
3. ANOVA Test & Tukey HSD
4. Residual Diagnostics
5. Interaction and Visualizations

Introduction

Benzodiazepines have shown to disrupt the positive effects of long term potentiation between cells on memory recall and learned associations. By differentiating the adverse long term effects of Alprazolam (long-term) and Triazolam (short-term), a better diagnosis may be administered to patients to mitigate any damage to the brain's metacognition and memory recall ability. Further research has also shown that simply recalling specific memories that are associated with strong emotions will cause said emotions to be materialized in present time and influence future thoughts for a short period (approximately 10 minutes). The presence of happy emotions and sad emotions are of interest and are known to affect memory recall significantly, thereby driving the question, what are the effects on memory recall performance from benzodiazepines after being primed with a happy or sad memory? This clinical study would show if the mood of memories aiding or hindering memory recall are independent of other factors, if benzodiazepines effectiveness are not only reliant on a participant's tolerance but also their mood, and finally the possibility of strengthening or worsening memory recall performance when presented together beyond the known response with the use of benzodiazepines or mood related memories on their own.

Background information (optional-read)

For most human beings that partake a role within a social environment with pressures and expectations, anxiety is a natural and sometimes an advantageous byproduct. Others may succumb to anxiety through a genetic disposition or a radical manipulation of brain chemistry from traumatic experiences, yet nevertheless anxiety is a natural occurrence, until its levels exceed the threshold for a medical disorder. The World Health Organization states that 1 in 13 globally suffer from anxiety which is known to be the most common mental disorder worldwide. While there are scores of research done on medication directed on treating anxiety through benzodiazepines or selective serotonin re-uptake inhibitors, extensive knowledge is known of the adverse effects of its long term use on memory recall performance and metacognition. In this study, Alprazolam and Triazolam will be of interest on memory recall performance.

Memory recall performance is attributed to numerous myelinated neurons acting concurrently from different regions in the brain for informational retrieval. However for the sake of specificity and simplicity, the concentration will be focused on the hippocampus and their interaction with benzodiazepine. Both Alprazolam (long-term effect) and Triazolam (short-term effect) are (GABA)_A receptor agonists due to their ability to bind to (GABA)_A receptors to lock a conformation causing the neurotransmitter GABA to have a higher affinity for the (GABA)_A receptors. This process initiates the inhibitory effects of GABA leading to sedative and anxiolytic effects. These receptors are found in the subunits of the hippocampus, the hormonal organ that is also connected to emotion. The powerful influence of recalling an emotionally driven memory on an individual's present thoughts and actions fall in line with the mood congruency effect, which is the psychological phenomenon in which an individual tends to associate future actions or thoughts that is consistent with the particular mood the memory has resurfaced onto the conscious level. Therefore, the mood an individual has during memory recall and the mood related to the memory itself is of major importance and influence on recalling performance.

Therefore, this study evaluates the effects of benzodiazepines on memory recall when being primed with happy or sad memories. According to previous research, there is evidence supporting more activation of the striatum for happy memories but higher accuracy in memory recall for sad memories. I predict that the highest dosage with Alprazolam, a long-term effect benzodiazepine, paired with a priming of happy memories prior to testing will illicit the worse performance while the control group primed with sad memories would illicit the best performance on memory recall

Load needed libraries and read in data

In [1]:

```
library(tidyverse)
library(png)
library(grid)

data <-
read.csv("../input/memory-test-on-drugged-islanders-data/Islander_data.csv")
```

```
— Attaching packages — tidyverse
1.2.1 —
✓ ggplot2 3.2.0.9000    ✓ purrr 0.3.2
✓ tibble 2.1.3          ✓ dplyr 0.8.3
✓ tidyr 0.8.3           ✓ stringr 1.4.0
✓ readr 1.3.1           ✓ forcats 0.4.0

— Conflicts —
tidyverse_conflicts() —
✗ dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
✗ dplyr::lag()     masks stats::lag()
```

Data Exploration & Design

Take a look into what type of data we are dealing with

In [2]:

```
cat("The data dimension's are ", dim(data)[1], " by ", dim(data)[2])
```

```
The data dimension's are 198 by 9
```

In [3]:

```
str(data)
```

```
'data.frame': 198 obs. of 9 variables:
 $ first_name : Factor w/ 139 levels "Aaron","Adam",...: 21 44 48 55
66 77 17 60 64 83 ...
 $ last_name : Factor w/ 18 levels "Bernard","Carrasco",...: 2 2 2 2
2 2 5 5 5 5 ...
 $ age : int 25 52 29 50 52 37 35 38 29 36 ...
 $ Happy_Sad_group : Factor w/ 2 levels "H","S": 1 2 1 2 1 2 2 1 1 2 ...
 $ Dosage : int 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ...
 $ Drug : Factor w/ 3 levels "A","S","T": 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ...
...
 $ Mem_Score_Before: num 63.5 41.6 59.7 51.7 47 66.4 44.1 76.3 56.2 54.8
...
 $ Mem_Score_After : num 61.2 40.7 55.1 51.2 47.1 58.1 56 74.8 45 75.9
...
 $ Diff : num -2.3 -0.9 -4.6 -0.5 0.1 -8.3 11.9 -1.5 -11.2
21.1 ...
```

In [4]:

```
head(data)
```

	first_name	last_name	age	Happy_Sad_group	Dosage	Drug	Mem_Score_Before	Mem_Score_After	Diff
	<fct>	<fct>	<int>	<fct>	<int>	<fct>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>

1	Bastian	Carrasco	25	H	1	A	63.5	61.2	-2.3
2	Evan	Carrasco	52	S	1	A	41.6	40.7	-0.9
3	Florencia	Carrasco	29	H	1	A	59.7	55.1	-4.6
4	Holly	Carrasco	50	S	1	A	51.7	51.2	-0.5
5	Justin	Carrasco	52	H	1	A	47.0	47.1	0.1
6	Liam	Carrasco	37	S	1	A	66.4	58.1	-8.3

Factor Design of Experiment

alpha, power, effect size, sample size

In [5]:

```
setwd("../input")
img1 <- readPNG("../input/images-island/plot6.png")
grid.raster(img1)
```


We decided to use a power of .8, which means that the probability that we will correctly reject the false null hypothesis. We used an alpha level of .05, which is the probability of falsely rejecting the null hypothesis. We used a conservative effect size of .25, which is a way of quantifying the difference between groups. We will be using a two-way complete block design. Using GPower (software), we determined that the sample size required is 197, based on the factor with the largest degree of freedom (4 for interaction). However, to have a balanced design, we will have a sample size of 198, so that each group will have 11 samples.

In [6]:

```
img2 <- readPNG('../input/images-island/plot.png')
grid.raster(img2)
```


ANOVA Test & Tukey HSD

We will be using the ANOVA function through R to test for any statistical significance using an alpha of 0.05. We will be testing the variance of means between types of drug and levels of dosage while maintaining a control in order to compare our results. We will also test for any sort of interaction between type of drug and dosage level.

In [7]:

```
#[Table 1] Analysis of Variance of Means
```

```
m1 <- aov(data = data, Diff ~ factor(Dosage) + Drug + Happy_Sad_group +
factor(Dosage):Drug)
summary(m1)
```

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)	
factor(Dosage)	2	1222	610.9	9.492	0.000118	***
Drug	2	4314	2156.9	33.513	3.56e-13	***

```

Happy_Sad_group      1      8      8.0    0.124 0.725429
factor(Dosage):Drug  4    5142  1285.5  19.973 1.01e-13 ***
Residuals            188  12100    64.4

```

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Table 1: Two-Way Randomized Block ANOVA with Interaction. Using an alpha significance of 0.05, the ANOVA analysis has shown that Dosage and Drug were significant as their p-values were 0.000118 and 3.56e-13 respectively. We also found that the interaction between the two were significant with a p-value of 1.01e-13. Lastly, the happy and sad memory block was found to be insignificant with a p-value of 0.7245429, showing that our blocking was ineffective.

In [8]:

```

#[Table 2] Tukey HSD
TukeyHSD(m1)

```

```

Tukey multiple comparisons of means
 95% family-wise confidence level

```

```

Fit: aov(formula = Diff ~ factor(Dosage) + Drug + Happy_Sad_group +
factor(Dosage):Drug, data = data)

```

```

$`factor(Dosage)`
      diff      lwr      upr      p adj
2-1 1.611827 -1.6750576 4.898712 0.4795112
3-1 5.899403  2.5998058 9.199000 0.0001104
3-2 4.287576  0.9756924 7.599459 0.0071642

```

```

$Drug
      diff      lwr      upr      p adj
S-A -9.6787307 -12.965616 -6.391846 0.0000000
T-A -10.0429699 -13.342567 -6.743373 0.0000000
T-S -0.3642393  -3.676123  2.947644 0.9634785

```

```

$Happy_Sad_group
      diff      lwr      upr      p adj

```

S-H 0.4010144 -1.848351 2.65038 0.725469

\$`factor(Dosage):Drug`

	diff	lwr	upr	p adj
2:A-1:A	5.5832421	-1.924944	13.09142795	0.3275251
3:A-1:A	22.3392001	14.831014	29.84738593	0.0000000
1:S-1:A	2.0877876	-5.420398	9.59597340	0.9941139
2:S-1:A	-1.0560702	-8.564256	6.45211568	0.9999599
3:S-1:A	-2.4501122	-9.958298	5.05807366	0.9831333
1:T-1:A	-1.5426181	-9.050804	5.96556775	0.9993077
2:T-1:A	0.8453424	-6.662844	8.35352821	0.9999928
3:T-1:A	-2.0220492	-9.621055	5.57695682	0.9956421
3:A-2:A	16.7559580	9.164806	24.34710974	0.0000000
1:S-2:A	-3.4954545	-11.086606	4.09569721	0.8786812
2:S-2:A	-6.6393123	-14.230464	0.95183948	0.1395984
3:S-2:A	-8.0333543	-15.624506	-0.44220254	0.0291325
1:T-2:A	-7.1258602	-14.717012	0.46529155	0.0846111
2:T-2:A	-4.7378997	-12.329051	2.85325201	0.5740047
3:T-2:A	-7.6052913	-15.286282	0.07569969	0.0545764
1:S-3:A	-20.2514125	-27.842564	-12.66026078	0.0000000
2:S-3:A	-23.3952703	-30.986422	-15.80411850	0.0000000
3:S-3:A	-24.7893123	-32.380464	-17.19816052	0.0000000
1:T-3:A	-23.8818182	-31.472970	-16.29066643	0.0000000
2:T-3:A	-21.4938577	-29.085009	-13.90270597	0.0000000
3:T-3:A	-24.3612493	-32.042240	-16.68025829	0.0000000
2:S-1:S	-3.1438577	-10.735009	4.44729403	0.9303983
3:S-1:S	-4.5378997	-12.129051	3.05325201	0.6310388
1:T-1:S	-3.6304057	-11.221557	3.96074610	0.8539933
2:T-1:S	-1.2424452	-8.833597	6.34870656	0.9998727
3:T-1:S	-4.1098368	-11.790828	3.57115424	0.7584718
3:S-2:S	-1.3940420	-8.985194	6.19710974	0.9996978
1:T-2:S	-0.4865479	-8.077700	7.10460383	0.9999999
2:T-2:S	1.9014125	-5.689739	9.49256428	0.9971358
3:T-2:S	-0.9659790	-8.646970	6.71501196	0.9999831
1:T-3:S	0.9074941	-6.683658	8.49864584	0.9999886
2:T-3:S	3.2954545	-4.295697	10.88660630	0.9103325
3:T-3:S	0.4280630	-7.252928	8.10905398	1.0000000
2:T-1:T	2.3879605	-5.203191	9.97911221	0.9866684
3:T-1:T	-0.4794311	-8.160422	7.20155989	0.9999999
3:T-2:T	-2.8673916	-10.548383	4.81359943	0.9614827

Table 2: Post-Hoc Analysis of Differences in Change of Memory Recall with Tukey HSD. A

Tukey HSD test was used to correctly adjust for the accumulation of type 1 error alphas and found that the Sugar-Alprazolam and Triazolam-Alprazolam comparisons were to be found significant, while the Triazolam-Sugar comparison was not significant with a p-value of 0.9623785 that provides insufficient evidence that there is a meaningful difference between the two.

Residual Diagnostics

In [9]:

```
#[Figure 1] Residual Diagnostics for Model Validity  
par(mfrow = c(2,2))  
plot(m1)
```


Figure 1 Summary Plots for Residuals of ANOVA Analysis. Portrayed are the plotting of residuals, the normal Q-Q plot, the Standardized Residuals, and the Leverage plot. The residual plot lacks any pattern and the variance follows a pattern of constancy. The Q-Q plot shows a slight problem in normality at the tail ends, however is assumed to be sufficient.

In [10]:

```
#Data Wrangling to allocate the mean difference in memory score  
#for each drug into variables for interaction plot
```

```
#Alprazolam  
A1 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage == 1, Drug == "A") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Alpra1_mean <- A1[2]  
A2 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage ==2, Drug == "A") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Alpra2_mean <- A2[2]  
A3 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage == 3, Drug == "A") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Alpra3_mean <- A3[2]
```

```
#Triazolam  
T1 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage == 1, Drug == "T") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Triaz1_mean <- T1[2]  
T2 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage == 2, Drug == "T") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Triaz2_mean <- T2[2]  
T3 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage ==3, Drug == "T") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Triaz3_mean <- T3[2]
```

```
#Sugar Tablet  
S1 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage ==1 ,Drug == "S") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Sugar1_mean <- S1[2]  
S2 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage ==2, Drug == "S") %>%  
  summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Sugar2_mean <- S2[2]
```

```
S3 <- data %>% group_by(Dosage) %>% filter(Dosage ==3, Drug == "S") %>%  
summarise(mean = mean(Diff))  
Sugar3_mean <- S3[2]
```

Interactions and Visualization

In [11]:

```
#[Figure 2] Plot the interaction plot between drug means for memory score  
difference  
x <- seq(1,3, by = 1)  
y <- c(Alpra1_mean, Alpra2_mean, Alpra3_mean)  
plot(x,y, type = "l", ylab = "Average Difference", xlab = "Dosage", main =  
"Interaction Plot", ylim = c(-5,25))  
lines(x, c(Triaz1_mean, Triaz2_mean, Triaz3_mean), type = "l", lty = 2,  
col = "blue")  
lines(x, c(Sugar1_mean, Sugar2_mean, Sugar3_mean), type = "l", lty = 12,  
col = "red")  
legend(1,25,legend = c("Alprazolam", "Triazolam", "Sugar"), col =  
c("black", "blue", "red"), lty = c(1,2,12))
```


Figure 2: Interaction plot of Dosage and Treatment with Average Differences in Memory Recall as the Response. The figure portays an interaction of the Control with all three treatments (Alprazolam, Triazolam and Control), however only Alprazolam shares an interaction with the Control.

The interaction plot reveals the relationship between the different treatments along with their varying dosages, as the Control had an interaction cross with all other variables. The Alprazolam drug had the widest range in variance of means but did not have an interaction with Triazolam.

In [12]:

```
#[Figure 3]
img3 <- readPNG('../input/images-island2/plot5.png')
grid.raster(img3)
```


Figure 3: Results Visualization - Boxplots. A side by side Boxplot of Average Differences in Memory Recall response time in seconds from the perspective of the drug treatment, happy and sad block, and the dosage treatment. Dots behind the bolded black lines which represent the 1st and 3rd quartiles are outliers and the midpoint of the blue box is the median.

The box plots constructed from the data helps visually digest the average differences between treatments, dosages, and the blocking factor by establishing them side by side. There was greater variability within the Alprazolam drug treatment, showing a huge detriment to memory recall abilities when paired with a higher dosage. The happy or sad memory blocking factor look to be identical, displaying no effect on the average differences in memory recall.

FIN - Thank you.